

QUIZ**LAST NAME: WANN****FIRST NAME: ABDOU****PROGRAM CODE: MBAIF****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author used Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 360 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which of the following is, according to Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, the correct definition of in-text citation?**

- It is the citing a piece of work within the actual text itself.¹**
- It is the act of mentioning authors' names after writing.
- It is acknowledging those who support your writing.
- It is a list of all sources of information at the end of a research.

2. **Kate L. Turabian discussed about some reasons for citation, which of the following is not mentioned in this regard?**

- Giving credit to authors or sources.
- Assure readers about accuracy of facts.
- To demonstrate your writing skills.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 6.

- To help readers follow or extend the research.
3. **Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma in their recognition on how to avoid plagiarism, which of the following is correct?**
- To properly cite the author(s) or source that has provided the information.³**
- Include the authors name and source in the reference list.
- To exactly copy the text of a source when paraphrasing then cites.
- To take permission from author(s) before using any information.
4. **Gulma and Cleenewerck in their identification of common errors in research papers, which of the following is not mentioned?**
- Do not use direct quotes.
- Avoid irrelevant information.
- Avoid inaccurate word or phrase.
- Put your work aside for some time before editing.⁴**
5. **Kate L. Turabian in her recommendation for the use of punctuations during parenthetical citation, which of the following is correct?**
- Separate most elements with periods.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff., 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 6.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 5-11.

- Put punctuation between the author and the date.
- Not to use punctuation mark between the author and the date.**⁵
- Not to separate the date and the page number with a comma.
6. **Which of the following best defines Reference List according to Gulma and Cleenewerck?**
- It is a list of all sources cited in a work.**⁶
- It is a list of all sources consulted during research.
- It is a list of sources used to write a research but not cited.
- It is a list of sources that an instructor or faculty recommend for a research.
7. **According to the European Commission, which of the following is a correct rule for the use of English language?**
- Do not use a question mark in indirect speech.**⁷
- Question mark is needed after a request and instruction.
- Question mark can be used in indirect speech.
- Question mark should not be closed up to the preceding word.
8. **Paraphrasing according to Gulma and Cleenewerck can be defined as**
- Presenting another person's ideas in your own ideas.**⁸

⁵ Turabian, 128.

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 59.

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission, 2011), 19.

- Using someone's ideas as express in the original text.
 - Using another person's ideas without citing.
 - Making best use of synonyms to replace someone's ideas in a research.
9. **Which of the following is, according to the European Commission the correct use of English Language?**
- Full stop is required when a sentence end with an abbreviation.
 - Use colons at the end of headings.
 - Colon requires that the next word to start with capital.
 - Do not use colons at the end of headings.⁹**
10. **Which of the following is not mentioned by Cleenewerck and Gulma in their recognition of some rule of Thumb for writing papers?**
- Write clearly.
 - Take the view you are discussing seriously.
 - Make best use of word power.¹⁰**
 - Do not plagiarize.

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 56.

⁹ European Commission, 15.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14-16.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. European Commission, 2011.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.